

SPOKE 1

FLYING WITHOUT A PASSPORT: A FUTURE OF EFFICIENCY OR A PRIVACY NIGHTMARE

Revision	Date	Authors
Rev01	29/09/2025	F. De Bosio, F. Bosco
Rev02	22/10/2025	R. Redondi

Finanziato dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca

Italiadomani
PIANO NAZIONALE DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA

Summary

1. INTRODUCTION	3
2. USE OF BIOMETRIC DATA IN AVIATION	4
2.1 WHAT BIOMETRIC DATA ARE AND WHY THEY ARE A 'SPECIAL CATEGORY'	4
2.2 BIOMETRICS AS A RESPONSE TO AIRPORT 'BOTTLENECKS'	4
2.3 WHERE BIOMETRICS HAS COME TO PLAY IN THE AIR TRAVEL SYSTEM	4
3. EXPECTED BENEFITS	6
4. MARKET BARRIERS	8
4. STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED	10
5. CASE STUDIES MAPPING	12
5.1. LINATE AIRPORT FACE BOARDING PILOT BY SEA	12
5.2. NAPOLI AIRPORT, THE LAUNCH OF FACEPASS BY GESAC.....	14
6. THE BIOMETRIC ISSUE IN EUROPE	15
6.1 THE FRENCH DATA PROTECTION AUTHORITY'S INITIATIVE	15
7. CONCLUSIONS	17

1. Introduction

In recent years, the air transport sector is facing safety and operational efficiency increasing challenges due to stringent regulation, rising customer expectations and pressure on margins. Moreover, the covid19 pandemic has left the mark in the aviation sector by fast-tracking digital innovation and more importantly has left passengers seeking for a touchless journey. From a passenger traffic standpoint, the industry has proven to be ever more resilient with passenger volumes now exceeding pre-pandemic levels, especially during summer peak season across Europe. However, passengers are now accustomed to fast airport journeys and ever less willing to accept traditional air travel journey bottlenecks. However, geopolitical circumstances are calling for stringent safety & security measures. The combination of these factors is calling for disruptive innovations. In particular, the recent rise in passenger traffic seen across Europe in the post Pandemic wave, the need to reduce waiting times, and the urgency to ensure high protection standards have pushed airports and airlines to experiment with new technological solutions. Among these, biometric recognition has emerged as one of the most promising innovations.

Biometrics, based on the unique identification of an individual through physical or behavioral characteristics—such as face, fingerprints, or voice—is proposed as a tool capable of streamlining boarding processes, reducing bottlenecks at security checks, and raising the reliability of passenger authentication. In a context where the traveler experience is increasingly central and pressure on airports grows year after year, these advantages take on strategic importance.

However, the introduction of biometric recognition in airports raises critical questions regarding privacy and personal data protection. Biometric technologies rely on the collection and processing of highly sensitive information, the inherently immutable nature of which (one cannot “change” a face or fingerprint as one can with passwords) makes security a particularly critical issue. This has sparked a heated debate between those emphasizing the benefits in terms of speed and security and those concerned about risks of pervasive surveillance and misuse of data.

In Europe, this debate takes place within a particularly strict regulatory framework, defined by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which imposes stringent restrictions on the collection, storage, and processing of biometric data. Airports and industry operators must therefore balance two seemingly opposing needs: on one side, the drive for innovation and efficiency; on the other, respect for fundamental rights to privacy and personal data protection.

The aim of this paper is to analyze the application of biometric recognition in airports, highlighting the benefits and obstacles associated with its implementation. In particular, the analysis will focus on privacy-related implications, examining how the stakeholders involved—institutions, airport operators, airlines, and regulatory authorities—are addressing the challenge of reconciling technological innovation with regulatory compliance. Through a comparison of concrete cases, such as Naples and Linate airports, and the European debate, including the case of the French data protection authority, the paper seeks to provide an in-depth and balanced view of the phenomenon, aiming to outline possible future scenarios for the adoption of biometrics in the airport sector.

2. Use of Biometric Data in aviation

2.1 What biometric data are and why they are a 'special category'

Biometric data is information derived from a person's physical, physiological, or behavioral characteristics that allow for unique identification. The most common examples include fingerprints, facial geometry, iris scans, voice patterns, and signature dynamics.

From a regulatory perspective, the *General Data Protection Regulation* (GDPR) classifies biometric data as a "special category of personal data" (Art. 9), as their processing carries high risks for the fundamental rights and freedom of individuals. Unlike a password or identity card, a biometric datum cannot be changed if compromised: if an individual's face is copied or misused, the violation is irreversible. This feature makes such information extremely sensitive and imposes strict obligations regarding purpose limitation, data minimization, security, and informed consent.

2.2 Biometrics as a response to airport 'bottlenecks'

The traditional airport process involves numerous verification steps—from check-in to document control, security, and boarding—that often create bottlenecks and slowdowns, particularly at high-traffic airports.

Biometrics aims to overcome these inefficiencies through a "single digital identity" model that accompanies the passenger throughout all stages of the journey. In this way, the face or fingerprint becomes the "universal key" allowing the passenger to pass through various gates without needing to show the passport or boarding pass multiple times.

Airports are not the only environments where the movement of large numbers of people creates structural bottlenecks. The traditional air travel process—check-in, repeated document controls, security screening, and boarding—mirrors the same challenges faced by other industries that depend on both efficiency and trust. Maritime hubs face a similar challenge: cruise terminals must process thousands of passengers during embarkation, where biometrics now play an increasingly central role in avoiding congestion and ensuring secure identification. Even in hospitality and retail, the pressure to simplify customer flows is evident—hotels are testing facial recognition for automated check-in, while airport lounges and restaurants integrate biometric access to create smoother, personalized experiences.

These parallels highlight that aviation is part of a broader movement: industries with complex flows of people and sensitive transactions are converging on biometrics as a tool to reduce friction, enhance security, and reshape customer experience. What distinguishes airports is the intensity of the stakes: few other environments demand the same balance of operational efficiency, global-scale security, and passenger trust.

2.3 Where Biometrics has come to play in the air travel system

The airport travel experience is structured around a series of mandatory stages, each of which can become a potential point of congestion. Biometrics is gradually being integrated into this journey, offering solutions aimed at making each phase faster, safer, and more seamless.

The journey begins at **check-in**, where the passenger links their biometric data to their travel document. A facial scan or fingerprint thus becomes a digital key, replacing in large part the need to repeatedly present a passport or boarding pass. This reduces waiting times at the counters and paves the way for increasingly autonomous check-in methods, such as self-service kiosks or dedicated mobile apps.

Moving on to **security screening**, biometrics comes into play again. The previously collected data is compared with the live facial scan, enabling a faster and more secure passage. Compared to a visual check of a document, biometric authentication provides a higher level of reliability and reduces human error.

For passengers on **international flights**, an additional stage is represented by **border controls**. Biometric e-gates, now widespread in many airports, accelerate passport verification and reduce the workload of border police, while simultaneously increasing the capacity to manage passenger flows.

Another crucial stage is **bag drop**, where some airports are experimenting with biometric kiosks that link luggage directly to the passenger's identity. This ensures greater traceability and reduces the need for dedicated staff, contributing to more efficient operations.

At the **boarding gate**, biometrics finds its most visible application. With so-called "face boarding," passengers can access the aircraft via a simple facial scan, without presenting any documents. Trials have shown significant reductions in boarding times and a positive perception among travelers, who experience the process as smoother and less stressful.

Beyond the main passenger journey stages, biometrics is also expanding into ancillary services. Some operators use it for lounge access, while others are testing it for contactless payments or personalized shopping in commercial areas. At the operational level, the same technologies are applied to airport staff to regulate access to restricted areas and sensitive zones, such as runways and control centers.

From this perspective, biometrics does not merely optimize individual stages; it redefines the entire travel experience, creating a digital continuum that accompanies the passenger from airport entry to boarding, and beyond.

3. Expected benefits

The introduction of biometric systems in airports brings numerous benefits, affecting both airport operations and the passenger experience. The technology allows for optimized passenger flows, improved accuracy of verifications, and, more generally, a smoother and safer travel experience.

Below are the main expected benefits that biometric applications can generate.

The introduction of biometric systems in airports brings a wide range of advantages, both for operational management and for the passenger experience. By reducing the need to show documents multiple times, biometrics can cut average boarding times by up to 40% and security check times by 30%, allowing airports to manage capacity more efficiently and mitigate bottlenecks that often generate delays. The accuracy of biometric verification surpasses that of manual document checks, lowering the risk of fraud and improving the ability to detect potential threats, while digital logs ensure transparency and accountability for any investigative needs. For passengers, the experience becomes smoother and less stressful, as repetitive steps such as presenting tickets and passports are eliminated, with over 70% of travelers reporting positive perceptions when queues are reduced and the journey is simplified.

From an operational perspective, once the initial investment is amortized, biometric systems reduce the need for staff dedicated to manual checks, decrease errors, and generate indirect cost savings. They also offer scalability, enabling airports to handle variable passenger flows without proportionally increasing staff or infrastructure, ensuring operational continuity during peak periods or extraordinary events. The adoption of international standards such as ICAO and IATA OneID promotes interoperability between airports and airlines, making global travel more seamless and consistent. Finally, biometrics opens the door to personalized services, including priority boarding, automated lounge access, and customized commercial offers, enhancing the perceived value of the passenger journey.

MISSIONE 4
ISTRUZIONE
RICERCA

BENEFIT	AIRPORT OPERATIONS	CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE
<i>Reduced check-in & security times</i>	●	●
<i>Faster boarding (Face Boarding)</i>	●	●
<i>Accuracy & Safety</i>	●	
<i>Smooth passenger journey</i>		●
<i>Operational cost reduction & scalability</i>	●	
<i>Standardization & interoperability</i>	●	
<i>Personalization & service enhancement</i>		●
<i>Passenger demand for innovation</i>		●

● High impact ● Medium impact ● Low impact

4. Market barriers

Alongside these benefits, the introduction of biometric recognition faces several obstacles, concerning technological, economic, regulatory, and ethical dimensions.

- **Costs and infrastructure**
Implementation requires significant investments for purchasing advanced hardware and software, integrating with existing systems, and training staff. Maintenance and system updates also represent additional costs.
- **Security and risk of data compromise**
Unlike a password, biometric data is immutable: if compromised, it cannot be replaced. It is therefore essential to ensure high security standards in the collection, storage, and processing of data. Any breach can have permanent consequences for individuals.
- **Data governance**
Who stores the data? For how long? With what guarantees of deletion? Despite the GDPR imposing stringent rules, significant operational challenges remain, especially when data must be shared among airports, airlines, and technology providers.
- **Passenger acceptance**
Some travelers perceive biometrics as an advantage, others as a threat to their privacy. The willingness to use these systems does not always come from customer demand but is often driven by the airports themselves, creating potential friction.
- **Interoperability among systems and stakeholders**
Not all airports and airlines use the same technological standards, limiting the possibility of a uniform experience at the international level.
- **Cultural resistance and social perception**
In some contexts, biometrics is seen more as a surveillance tool than as a positive innovation, slowing down adoption.
- **Risk of algorithmic bias**
Some facial recognition systems show higher error rates depending on ethnicity, gender, or age, raising issues of fairness and discrimination.
- **Dependence on external technology partners**
Reliance on large global vendors raises questions about data sovereignty and the airport's ability to maintain full control over information.
- **Divergent national regulations**
Even within the GDPR framework, national data protection authorities may apply rules and levels of strictness differently, creating uncertainty and hindering uniform implementation

Biometric recognition in airports offers significant potential for improving efficiency, security, and the passenger experience, but its adoption involves complex challenges. Success depends not only on technology but also on airports' ability to build passenger trust and reconcile innovation with the protection of fundamental rights.

In particular, recent studies show that a significant percentage of travelers support the adoption of biometric systems, appreciating their ability to reduce waiting times and simplify the travel process. This preference makes the technology a perceived advantage, as it directly addresses customer needs and can significantly enhance the passenger experience.

However, while passenger acceptance of biometric technologies appears high, the question of willingness to pay introduces a more complex perspective. Services such as airport fast track have already established themselves as well-integrated solutions, for which travelers are accustomed to paying a premium in exchange for time savings and convenience. In contrast, there is currently little empirical evidence to suggest that passengers would be willing to pay directly for biometric solutions. This raises the question of whether biometrics should be positioned as a premium, paid service or as a basic infrastructure integrated into the passenger journey. Currently, the competitive benchmark remains fast track, a well-accepted solution already integrated into airport operations and passenger travel routines. However, its scope is limited to certain stages, primarily security checks. The true competitive advantage of biometric systems could emerge at those touchpoints not covered by fast track, such as border control and boarding, where airports and airlines currently have little flexibility to innovate. By extending efficiency gains to these traditionally rigid stages, biometrics can position itself not only as an alternative to existing services, but also as a transformative solution with broader reach.

Passenger willingness does not eliminate privacy and personal data protection challenges, which remain a concrete obstacle to implementation. Biometric data are considered sensitive under the GDPR, and their processing requires strict standards for security, informed consent, data minimization, and continuous audit procedures. Consequently, even if adoption is desired by travelers, airports must face significant technical and regulatory complexities, invest in secure infrastructure, and implement continuous updates to ensure compliance. Equally important is the definition of clear data management and governance policies and procedures. This represents a particularly complex task for airport operators, which are not "digital-native" organizations and often lack the internal structures and operating models required to design, maintain, and enforce policies of this kind. Building this capability is therefore an additional—and substantial—layer of effort that conditions the sustainable adoption of biometric solutions.

4. Stakeholders involved

The adoption of biometrics in airports does not concern only travelers or airport operators but involves a complex ecosystem of stakeholders. Each actor brings their own objectives, expectations, and concerns, which can sometimes converge but at other times diverge. For this reason, the success of biometric systems cannot rely solely on technological advancement but requires a coordinated and shared approach to ensure that sensitive biometric data are managed ethically, securely, and in compliance with regulations. Only through such cooperation can biometric innovation be implemented in a way that is both effective and socially sustainable.

1. Airport operators

Airports are the primary promoters of biometrics, driven by the need to optimize passenger flows and reduce congestion in terminal spaces. For airport operators, the technology is a lever to increase operational efficiency and maintain competitiveness especially for international hubs where passengers often need to go through more touch points across their journey towards the destination. However, their push for innovation must be balanced with the need to comply with data protection regulations, investing in secure infrastructure and ensuring traveler trust.

2. Airlines

Airlines are interested in biometrics because it reduces boarding times, improves punctuality, and enhances passenger satisfaction. The promise of a smoother travel experience strengthens the airline's image and its ability to retain customers. The main challenge for airlines lies in the fragmentation of technological standards: each airport may adopt different solutions, making integration and the creation of a uniform global experience complex.

3. Security authorities and law enforcement

For security authorities, biometrics is a fundamental tool for ensuring more reliable identification and preventing document fraud. From their perspective, innovation strengthens national and international security, providing new tools for border control. At the same time, authorities face the delicate task of balancing risk prevention with respect for travelers' fundamental rights, avoiding a slide toward excessively invasive control.

4. Data protection authorities and regulatory bodies

The role of data protection authorities is crucial to ensure that the use of biometric data complies with the GDPR. These institutions evaluate pilot projects, issue guidelines, and, when necessary, impose corrective measures. Their goal is to guarantee the legality and proportionality of sensitive data processing. Their challenge is twofold: promoting the protection of rights while harmonizing rules and interpretations across European countries, preventing regulatory differences from hindering the deployment of common solutions.

The consequences of non-compliance with the GDPR framework are particularly severe: companies and airport operators processing biometric data without adequate safeguards may face fines of up to €20 million or 4% of their annual global turnover, whichever is higher. In addition to financial penalties, violations can result in reputational damage, restrictions on data processing, and the suspension of projects. This regulatory risk reinforces the need for airports and airlines to adopt robust governance models and proactive compliance strategies when deploying biometric systems.

5. Passengers

Passengers are both beneficiaries and the most exposed to the risks of biometrics. Many travelers see innovation as a way to reduce waiting times and stress, expressing a preference for biometric systems over traditional document checks. Others, however, have concerns about the security of their data and fear potential misuse. Trust therefore becomes a decisive factor: without transparency and the ability to make an informed choice (opt-in or opt-out), acceptance of biometrics may decrease.

6. Technology providers

Companies developing facial recognition software and hardware for biometric gates are key players in the supply chain. Their goal is to expand the market and demonstrate the reliability of their solutions. However, they must address the challenge of ensuring accurate, bias-free algorithms, as well as IT systems capable of protecting highly sensitive data. A provider's reputation depends on their ability to offer innovation without compromising security.

7. International institutions and industry associations

Organizations such as ICAO and IATA promote the creation of global standards to ensure interoperability between airports and airlines. Associations like Airports Council International also play an advocacy role, supporting the interests of airports worldwide. Their function is to foster a shared framework, but the challenge remains to overcome regulatory and cultural differences across jurisdictions, which often hinder uniform adoption of the technology.

The stakeholder landscape demonstrates that airport biometrics is an innovation with a strong collective dimension. No single actor can define its success alone: achieving a balance between operational efficiency, security, and rights protection requires cooperation among airports, airlines, regulatory authorities, passengers, and civil society.

5. Case Studies mapping

Applications of biometric data in airports have expanded significantly over the last decade, primarily through temporary pilot projects aimed at testing new technologies and processes. Some of the most influential early pilots include trials at Schiphol Airport in the Netherlands, Hong Kong International Airport, and Changi Airport in Singapore, which have provided valuable insights into passenger experience, security, and operational efficiency. However, many of these biometric pilots have struggled to transition from limited trials to large-scale implementations, limiting the realization of the full potential of this disruptive innovation. Among the most recent initiatives of particular relevance to the Italian aviation sector are the biometric programs implemented at Linate Airport and Napoli Airport, which exemplify the ongoing efforts to integrate these technologies into everyday airport operations while addressing regulatory, technical, and organizational challenges.

5.1. Linate Airport face boarding pilot by SEA

Milan Linate Airport was one of the first in Italy to introduce a pilot Face Boarding project, designed to make access to gates faster and more intuitive. The system allowed passengers to register via a dedicated app or kiosk, linking their identity document with their facial biometric data. Once registration was completed, travelers could access security and boarding simply by walking in front of a recognition camera.

Despite the interest generated by the initiative and its alignment with practices already adopted at other European airports, the Italian Data Protection Authority ordered the suspension of the service. The decision was not based on opposition to biometrics per se, but on data protection design issues deemed non-compliant with the GDPR and with the recommendations of the European Data Protection Board (EDPB).

The concerns did not involve the technology itself, but non-compliance with GDPR rules. In particular, the Authority identified:

- Violation of the minimization principle, with the collection and storage of data exceeding the declared purpose;
- Lack of a solid legal basis and freely given, informed consent for processing biometric data, considered a “special category” under the law;
- Insufficient transparency toward passengers, who did not receive clear and complete explanations on how their data would be used and stored.

The decision was presented as a corrective measure, not a “no” to biometrics. The Authority’s message is clear: these technologies can be adopted, but only if designed in accordance with the principles of *privacy by design* and *data protection by default*.

Below the key findings from the Italian Data Protection Authority:

<i>Aspect</i>	<i>Involved GDPR principle</i>	<i>Identified issue</i>
Opaque information	Art. 12-13 GDPR (transparency and information)	Lack of clarity regarding purpose, retention periods and methods of data use
Weak legal basis	Art. 6-9 GDPR (lawfulness and special categories of data)	Failure to identify adequate legal bases for the processing of biometric data
Disproportionate collection	Art. 5(1)(c) GDPR (data minimization)	Data collection methods exceeding the actual needs of boarding procedures
Fragile consent	Art. 7 GDPR (conditions for consent)	Absence of guarantees for free, alternative, and revocable consent

5.2. Napoli airport, the launch of FacePass by GESAC

At Naples Airport, in November 2024, *Face Pass* was launched—a biometric recognition system initially implemented for passengers on Lufthansa flight LH 335 to Frankfurt. The project, developed by GESAC in collaboration with Lufthansa and specialized technology partners, enables registered travelers to pass through security checks and access the boarding gate using only facial recognition, without the need to present identity documents or boarding passes.

The system requires a pre-registration at a dedicated Face Pass kiosk within the Lufthansa check-in zone, where the passenger links their identity document and boarding pass to their facial biometric data. From that point on, the entire airport journey becomes touchless, with automated checks based solely on biometrics.

The project is still in an experimental phase and represents a concrete example of how Italian airports continue to invest in this technology, even within a very stringent regulatory context. Its continuation will depend on the promoters' ability to demonstrate full GDPR compliance and to ensure transparency, voluntary consent, and data security.

These cases highlight the critical need for a clear and standardized framework of data protection design principles, ensuring that biometric systems comply with Italian regulatory requirements while remaining aligned with broader European guidelines, such as those set by the European Data Protection Board (EDPB). Establishing such a framework would facilitate the safe and scalable deployment of biometric technologies in airports, balancing innovation with the protection of passengers' fundamental rights.

6. The Biometric issue in Europe

The use of biometrics in the airport context is not merely a national matter but part of a broader debate involving all European data protection authorities. Since the first pilot projects, the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) has highlighted the risks associated with processing biometric data, stressing that, as a “special category” under the GDPR, it requires particularly strict safeguards.

Facial recognition, in particular, has always been perceived as a technology with a strong impact on fundamental rights, as it introduces dynamics of surveillance and data collection that go far beyond traditional document verification. Hence the need, at the European level, to establish clear regulatory frameworks that distinguish between acceptable and unacceptable uses of biometric technologies.

6.1 The French Data Protection Authority's initiative

Within this context, the French Data Protection Authority (CNIL) has stood out for its proactive and systematic approach. Rather than reacting on a case-by-case basis, it decided to submit a set of concrete questions to the EDPB concerning the use of biometrics in airports, presenting four technically distinct scenarios:

1. **Data stored on personal devices:** biometric recognition with data kept only on the user’s device, under their exclusive control, for authentication purposes.
2. **Centralized database with key stored on the device:** encrypted biometric data in a database managed by the airport, with the decryption key stored only on the user’s device, for authentication.
3. **Centralized database with operator’s key:** encrypted biometric data in a database managed by the airport, with the key controlled by the operator, for identification purposes.
4. **Cloud database:** encrypted biometric data stored in the cloud by the operator or its provider, with the decryption key managed by the operator or provider, for identification purposes.

This approach proved crucial in providing operational clarity for the design and implementation of biometric systems, as it forced the EDPB to provide not only abstract assessments but also concrete operational guidelines. Effectively, it created a regulatory compass for all Member States, giving the sector clearer benchmarks for distinguishing between projects that comply with the GDPR and those that do not, and facilitating the deployment of viable biometric solutions at scale.

A key outcome of this debate is the distinction between authentication and identification, two profoundly different modes of using biometrics:

- **Authentication (1:1):** the biometric data provided by the passenger is compared with a single reference already associated with them (e.g., the face registered at check-in). This approach is less invasive, as it merely verifies correspondence between a person and their own data.
- **Identification (1:N):** the passenger’s face is compared against an entire database of profiles. This method entails far higher risks, as it exposes individuals to generalized surveillance and significant loss of control over their personal data.

Although this may appear to be a technical distinction, it has decisive consequences: while authentication can more easily be justified under the law, identification is far more difficult to reconcile with the GDPR principles of proportionality and data minimization.

EDPB examined the four scenarios of facial recognition use in airports, distinguishing between models deemed compatible and incompatible with the GDPR.

- **Compatible scenarios (1 and 2):** considered acceptable are systems in which control of the data remains firmly in the hands of the user. In practice, this means that the biometric data or the encryption key remains in the direct possession of the passenger, thereby minimizing the risk of misuse or unauthorized access.
- **Incompatible scenarios (3 and 4):** deemed non-compliant are models involving centralized storage of data or control by airport operators and cloud service providers. In these cases, the user effectively loses control of their information, significantly increasing risks of violations, misuse, and disproportionate surveillance.

The joint work of CNIL and the EDPB has set a benchmark at the European level. It has helped to establish more uniform European standards and to clarify the boundaries of legitimate use of biometrics in airports. The key lesson is that facial recognition is not inherently incompatible with European regulation, but its implementation requires specific design choices to ensure that passengers retain control over their data and that processing does not exceed what is strictly necessary.

For airports and technology providers, this means that the future of Face Boarding and similar tools will be possible only if supported by a user-centric data governance model that is transparent and consistent with the core principles of the GDPR.

7. Conclusions

Biometric recognition represents one of the most promising innovations in the airport sector, with the potential to radically transform the passenger experience and delivering operational excellence for airport operations by reducing pressure on ever-stretched air travel system bottle-necks. Successful cases demonstrate that the technology can lead to significant improvements in efficiency, security, and passenger satisfaction, responding to a growing demand for faster and more seamless processes.

However, as shown by the analysis of pilot projects and the decisions of supervisory authorities, these benefits cannot be separated from privacy and data protection concerns. Experiences at airports such as Linate and Naples have revealed that projects risk being suspended or scaled back not because biometrics are inherently unacceptable, but because design choices failed to comply with the fundamental principles of the GDPR—such as proportionality, data minimization, transparency, and informed consent.

The French CNIL's case and the guidelines developed by the EDPB confirm this view: European regulation is not an obstacle to technological progress but rather a framework that steers innovation toward more ethical and sustainable models. In this perspective, *privacy by design* and *privacy by default* are not bureaucratic formalities, but key levers for building biometric systems capable of balancing security needs with the protection of fundamental rights.

Another crucial factor is that true innovation cannot exist without building social trust. Projects developed without full compliance with regulatory principles risk reputational damage and additional costs, as demonstrated by cases where initiatives announced were never fully implemented. Compliance, therefore, is not an obstacle but the necessary condition for ensuring sustainability and public acceptance. Merely highlighting a single area of application is not enough: the real strategy for social acceptance lies in designing a fully integrated, end-to-end touchless journey, enabling passengers to perceive the benefits of biometrics across all stages of travel—from check-in to security, boarding, and access to services and commercial areas—while involving all relevant stakeholders. In this way, the technology is not presented as an isolated experiment but as part of a coherent, customer-centric ecosystem that maximizes perceived value, ensures alignment among stakeholders, and fosters a more inclusive and sustainable transition toward the airport of the future.

Looking ahead, it is increasingly clear that the path to widespread adoption of biometric recognition in airports will depend on the ability to develop GDPR-compliant models, such as those identified in scenarios 1 and 2 by the EDPB, where data control remains firmly in the hands of passengers. Only in this way can trust, legitimacy, and social acceptance of the technology be ensured.

Ultimately, biometrics are not a “false myth of blocked progress,” but a concrete reality that can help redefine the future of aviation. The essential condition is that they are implemented with transparency, proportionality, and accountability, placing human dignity and rights at the center. By doing so, European airports will not only adopt more efficient tools but also strengthen their relationship of trust with passengers, transforming technological innovation into genuine social progress.

References

A. Sharma, "What are the applications of biometrics In airports?" (2024), from: [What are the Applications of Biometrics in Airports?](#)

C. Burt, "Biometric check-ins and bag drop to arrive at majority of airports by 2026: SITA" (2025), from: [Biometric check-ins and bag drop to arrive at majority of airports by 2026: SITA | Biometric Update](#)

IATA, "Passengers want convenience and technology to Improve processes, regional preferences diverging" (2024), from: [IATA - Passengers Want Convenience and Technology to Improve Processes, Regional Preferences Diverging](#)

R. Golledge, "New Amadeus research reveals appetite for tech to enhance travel, skyrockets In 2025" (2025), from: [Appetite for Tech to enhance Travel skyrockets in 2025 | Amadeus](#)

ICA, "Passport-less clearance fully rolled-out Changi Airport" (2024), from: [Passport-less Clearance Now at All Changi Airport Terminals - Daily.SG](#)

HongKong International Airport, "Flight Token", from: [Flight Token, Passenger Guide - Hong Kong International Airport](#)

FutureTravelExperience, "KLM, AMS, IDEMIA e altri lanciano il progetto pilota transatlantico Digital Travel Credential per rendere i controlli più efficienti" (2024), from: [KLM, AMS, IDEMIA and more launch Digital Travel Credential pilot](#)

Altalex, "Art. 83 GDPR - Condizioni generali per infliggere sanzioni amministrative pecuniarie", from: [Art. 83 GDPR - Condizioni generali per infliggere sanzioni amministrative pecuniarie](#)

G. Ricci, "Riconoscimento facciale In aeroporto: scenari di compatibilità con il GDPR" (2024), from: [Riconoscimento facciale in aeroporto: scenari di compatibilità con il GDPR - Cyber Security 360](#)

T. Orrù, "Linate, Il faceboarding e il falso mito del 'progresso bloccato'" (2025), from: [Linate, il faceboarding e il falso mito del "progresso bloccato" - Cyber Security 360](#)

ANSA, "Aeroporto di Napoli: parte Face Pass, riconoscimento biometrico" (2024), from: [Aeroporto di Napoli: parte Face Pass, riconoscimento biometrico - Notizie - Ansa.it](#)